

A FIELD STUDY ON LEAF IONOME AND CALCIUM-RELATED GENE EXPRESSION PROFILES IN XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA-INFECTED OLIVE CULTIVARS

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Field observations carried out in Salento (Italy) in the area infected by *Xylella fastidiosa* (*Xf*) evidenced that olive trees of the cultivar 'Leccino' show milder symptoms, if compared to those observed in the susceptible cv. 'Ogliarola salentina'. A transcriptome profiling of the two cultivars infected with the *Xf* De Donno strain revealed different expression profiles of genes controlling calcium homeostasis. In particular, a calcium-dependent protein kinase (CDPK1) is highly overexpressed in 'Ogliarola salentina' infected leaves. Calcium is an important secondary messenger, whose downstream transduction pathways trigger different physiological processes, including stress response and plant defense. Moreover, previous studies have shown that Ca accumulation in leaves is associated with symptomatic tobacco, blueberry, grapes and pecan plants infected with *Xf*.

We pursued a field study that determined the ionome and CDPK1 expression levels of infected leaves of the cvs. 'Leccino' and 'Ogliarola salentina', to evaluate the correlation between Ca, Ca-mediated responses and disease severity in *Xf* olive infection.

Comparison between the two cultivars revealed changes in ionome and CDPK1 gene expression in symptomatic vs asymptomatic tissues. 'Leccino' symptomatic leaves had significant higher Ca concentration as compared to asymptomatic leaves, while differences for the susceptible cv. 'Ogliarola salentina' were non-significant. CDPK1 expression in 'Ogliarola salentina' was significantly increased relatively to 'Leccino' trees grown in the same field and the increase was higher in symptomatic leaves.

These data confirmed that, in olive, as previously observed in other species, Ca plays a role in disease progression. Moreover, *Xf* infection in olive induces a re-modeling of the ionome, which correlates with the degree of disease severity and the susceptibility of the cultivar.